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Semantic scene understanding and traversability estimation for off-road vehicles

Author:

Jesús Copado Rodríguez

Autonomous Systems MSc

Internal supervisor:

Zoltán Istenes, PhD

Associate Professor

External supervisor:

András László Majdik, PhD

Senior research fellow at SZTAKI

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FACULTY OF INFORMATICS

MASTER THESIS TOPIC DECLARATION FORM

Name of Student: Jesús Copado Rodríguez

Neptun code: EAYGE8

Training: Full-time

Technical major: Computer Science for Autonomous Systems

Email Address: jcr.22@hotmail.com

Phone Number: +34663725228

Name of ELTE supervisor: Zoltán Istenes

Workplace: ELTE – Faculty of Informatics

(Name of Entry-university supervisor: Quan Zhou)

Workplace: NA

Name of Industrial supervisor: András Madjik

Workplace: SZTAKI Machine Perception Research Lab

Information about the internship

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Title of the thesis

Semantic scene understanding and traversability estimation for off-road vehicles.

Topic of the thesis

In recent years a lot of research has been carried out by big tech companies in the field of autonomous driving. However, this scientific exploration has been conducted specially in cities or suburban areas and less attention has been given to unstructured off-road situations.

As mentioned in [1], to operate autonomously and intelligently in unstructured terrain, a robot or vehicle must possess many advanced navigational skills. In particular, it needs to have capability to perceive its surrounding environment, recognize hazardous terrain topography, discriminate negotiable and non-negotiable obstacles, and select suitable routes compatible with its mobility capabilities without jeopardizing its safety and mission.

Therefore, the goal of this project is to develop a spatial AI algorithm for off-road vehicles that is able to perceive and understand autonomously the real physical world by identifying the surrounding main surface and object classes (grass, meadow, dirt road, trail, bush, tree, etc.) and estimate their traversability using RGB and/or multispectral camera and/or LiDAR sensors.

Self driving vehicles require a deep understanding of their surroundings to a high-level pixel-wise accuracy. Hence, the aforementioned AI algorithm will probably consist of a semantic segmentation model, which assigns a predefined class to each pixel of an image. These models are usually built using Deep Learning techniques and, in particular, convolutional networks have been demonstrated to work notably well with image related problems. A further literature review will be conducted along with several tests and evaluation in order to identify an optimal architecture for this model to perform accurately in real-time scenarios.

Research questions

- Can the use of multispectral cameras on top of RGB images improve the results of the task of autonomous driving on off-road vehicles? What is the advantage?
- Can this actually work in an unstructured environment? Will the results be sufficiently accurate for an autonomous vehicle to be deployed?
- Is it possible to find optimal traversability? Will it be necessary to use LiDAR/depth data or is the multispectral camera enough in this scenario?

Tasks

- Semantic scene understanding and traversability estimation for off-road vehicles.
- Take part in data gathering and labeling.
- Perform literature survey and review.
- Develop and train a deep neural network for semantic segmentation.
- Evaluate the results and write the scientific report.
- Coding using C/C++, Python and/or Matlab.

Keywords

Semantic scene understanding and traversability estimation for off-road vehicles robot perception, machine learning, spatial AI

References

[1] A. Shirkhodaie, R. Amrani and E. Tunstel, "Soft computing for visual terrain perception and traversability assessment by planetary robotic systems", *2005 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics*, 2005.

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I approve of the suggested topic of the internship, and in the name of the institution (organization, company) above I agree, that the named student will carry out his/her internship along the conditions detailed above:

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.....

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I ask for the acceptance of my thesis topic.

Budapest, 17./02./2021

.....

Student

The topic of the thesis and internship is approved by the Department of ELTE Informatics

Budapest,/..../202

Digitálisan
aláírta: Dr.
Horváth Zoltán
Dátum:
2021.02.24
11:49:01 +01'00'

.....

Dr. Zoltán Horváth
Dean of Faculty of Informatics

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I hereby confirm the submission of the Master Thesis Work on the Computer Science MSc course with author and title:

Name of Student: **Jesús Copado Rodríguez**
Code of Student: **EAYGE8**
Title of Thesis: **Semantic scene understanding and traversability estimation for off-roadvehicles**
Supervisor: **Zoltán Istenes**
.....

at Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Informatics.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

In recent years a great amount of research has been carried out by big tech companies in the field of autonomous driving. However, this scientific exploration has been conducted specially in cities or suburban areas, where a well structured road network exists, and less attention has been given to unstructured off-road situations.

As mentioned in [1], to operate autonomously and intelligently in unstructured terrain, a robot or vehicle must possess many advanced navigational skills. In particular, it needs to have capability to perceive its surrounding environment, recognize hazardous terrain topography, discriminate between negotiable and non-negotiable obstacles, and select suitable routes compatible with its mobility capabilities without jeopardizing its safety and mission.

Therefore, the goal of this project is to develop a spatial AI algorithm for off-road vehicles that is able to perceive and understand autonomously the real physical world by identifying the surrounding main surface and object classes (grass, meadow, dirt road, trail, bush, tree, etc.) and estimate their traversability using RGB and/or multi spectral camera and/or LiDAR sensors.

Self driving vehicles require a deep understanding of their surroundings to a high-level pixel-wise accuracy. Hence, the aforementioned AI algorithm will probably

consist of a semantic segmentation model, which assigns a predefined class to each pixel of an image. These models are usually built using Deep Learning techniques and, in particular, convolutional networks have been demonstrated to work notably well with image related problems. A further literature review will be conducted along with several tests and evaluation in order to identify an optimal architecture for this model to perform accurately in real-time scenarios.

1.2 Research questions

- Can the use of multi-spectral cameras on top of RGB images improve the results of the task of autonomous driving on off-road vehicles? What is the advantage?
- What is currently the achievable accuracy of the semantic scene segmentation algorithms in an unstructured environment? Will the results be sufficiently accurate for an autonomous vehicle to be deployed?
- Is it possible to find optimal traversability? Will it be necessary to use LiDAR/depth data or is the multi-spectral camera enough in this scenario?

1.3 Objectives

- Take part in data gathering and labeling.
- Perform literature survey and review.
- Develop and train a deep neural network for semantic segmentation.
- Evaluate the results and write the scientific report.
- Coding using C/C++, Python and/or Matlab.

1.4 Contributions

- Background information on multi-modal image segmentation.
- Literature review on datasets and techniques for deep multimodal image segmentation, focusing on off-road scenarios.

- Strategy for accelerating the image annotation process.
- New annotated dataset for off-road autonomous perception, called Hungary Forest Dataset.
- Experiments and metrics of models trained on this new dataset.

1.5 Thesis structure

Chapter 2 provides necessary background knowledge on scene understanding and multimodal semantic segmentation together with a review of related work done particularly in the field of deep multimodal semantic segmentation for off-road vehicles. Chapter 3 goes through the steps taken to prepare and annotate the new data captured for this work as well as the tests carried out to assess the accuracy. Finally, chapter 4 concludes this work and proposes further research that can be conducted in the field.

Chapter 2

Background and literature review

2.1 Scene understanding

Scene understanding plays a very important role in applications such as autonomous driving or robot navigation on real-world environments [2]. Scenes are usually not simple, rather complex, encompassing multiple objects which may belong to different or similar classes, and these objects will have a relation with each other [3]. Scene understanding aims to analyse these scenes in a human-like fashion, providing accurate visual information and understanding the whole context of the scene [3]. Scene understanding is further divided into sub-problems: *semantic* scene understanding, which focuses purely on the semantic relationships between objects including the works in object recognition or semantic segmentation; and *geometric* scene understanding, which concentrates on the geometric properties and includes the works on pose estimation or dense reconstruction [4]. In this work I will attend to the first, semantic scene understanding, particularly in the case of autonomous driving in off-road scenarios.

Autonomous driving could provide benefits to both society and the individual, such as improved road safety, reduction of carbon emissions or decreased traffic congestion [5]. However, reaching the point of reliable autonomous systems is a difficult task [6]. The reason for this is that self-driving cars are intelligent agents

that need to perceive, predict, decide, plan and execute their decisions in the real world, usually in complex or uncontrolled environments [6], such as the one showed in Figure 2.3. In this situation, even a small error in the system can produce a fatality.

Figure 2.1: An illustration of semantic scene understanding of a complex urban scenario for autonomous driving. The driverless car uses multi-modal signals for perception, such as RGB camera images, LiDAR points, Radar points, and map information. Figure extracted from [6].

In the case of off-road unstructured environments such as a forest, although the possibility of the occurrence of a fatality is lower, navigation is even more complicated, as the self-driving agent needs to take more complex decisions. More concretely, the agent needs to decide whether it can be safely driven over some obstacles, such as tall grass or small bushes, or not, for the case of obstacles like boulders or tree trunks [2]. And to this moment, most of the research on semantic scene understanding has been concentrated on structured environments, such as urban road scenes and indoor environments, composed by scenes where the containing objects are rigid and have distinct geometric properties, which is not the case for a forested scenario [2]. Here, in this work I seek to make a contribution to the less-researched off-road unstructured scenario.

Both in structured and unstructured environments, perception systems in autonomous cars need to be:

- *accurate*: the information of the driving environment provided by the system must be precise.
- *robust*: their work should not be hindered by adverse weather situations weather that are not covered during training (open-set conditions), and neither in the case of degradation or faultiness of some of the sensors.
- *real-time*: more importantly when the cars are moving at high speed.

Towards these objectives, self-driving cars are often equipped with multi-modal sensors, such as cameras, LiDARs or Radars [6]. Resulting in vehicle setups such as the ones showed in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: (a) The Boss autonomous car at DARPA 2007 [7], (b) Waymo self-driving car [8], (c) Viona autonomous platform [2]

The vehicle setup used to record our dataset is similar to Figure 2.2(a), it consisted of a car with a multispectral sensor and RGB camera mounted on top of it, along with a LiDAR sensor. See section 3.1 for information on the sensor and data captured. The LiDAR data captured was not used in this work since the goal is to evaluate the capabilities of a setup consisting of only a multispectral camera. In this project, the focus was set on analysing the capabilities of the multispectral sensor and RGB camera alone, measuring how accurate can a model be without using the LiDAR sensor. However, the deployment of the model and the real use of it would be on a system more similar to 2.2(c).

Figure 2.3 showed an illustration of semantic scene understanding of a complex urban scenario for autonomous driving. In the figure both the applications of object detection, i.e. locating and classifying multiple objects in a scene [9], and semantic segmentation, i.e. assigning a semantic label to each pixel in the image [10], are depicted. For clarity purposes, not all bounding boxes and labels are drawn in the image [6].

As part of this thesis, I aim to train a multimodal semantic segmentation model for autonomous driving of off-road vehicles, so I will focus on reviewing the latest advancements regarding the task of semantic segmentation, rather than object detection or any other sub-problem of scene understanding. Firstly, in the next section (Section 2.2), a general review on semantic segmentation is presented, and after in the following section (Section 2.3), I will set the focus in a particular sub-case of semantic segmentation, called multimodal semantic segmentation. And finally, in Section 2.4, an overview of the most popular multimodal datasets is presented, emphasising on those with multispectral data.

2.2 Semantic segmentation

Semantic segmentation is one of the fundamental problems in computer vision and it is essential towards complete scene understanding for its application in tasks such as autonomous navigation in real-world environments [11]. The goal of semantic segmentation is to assign a semantic label (e.g. car, tree, person) to each pixel of an image [12]. This definition is further differentiated from instance-level segmentation, whose objective is to produce per-instance mask and class label [13], or panoptic segmentation, which is gaining attention recently and combines both pixel-level and instance-level semantic segmentation [14].

In the last decade, there has been a clear transition in semantic segmentation approaches from employing hand engineered features along with traditional machine learning algorithms such as Support Vector Machines [15], Boosting [16] or Random Forests [17], to deep learning techniques due to its much superior performance. A

deep neural network is a powerful tool that learns hierarchical feature representations given a large amount of data [18].

Figure 2.3: Illustration of a fully convolutional network applied to the task of semantic segmentation. Figure extracted from [19].

Particularly, the outstanding performance achieved by Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), a class of deep neural network [20], in classification tasks led to their application for dense prediction problems such as semantic segmentation or depth estimation [21]. One of the first end-to-end approaches that learns to directly map the low resolution representations from a classification network to a dense prediction output was the Fully Convolutional Network (FCN) model [19]. In this work, the fully-connected layers in a CNN classifier [20] used to predict classification scores are exchanged with convolutional layers to produce coarse output maps. These maps are then up-sampled to dense pixel labels by backwards convolution (also called deconvolution or transpose convolution).

Badrinarayanan, Kendall, and Cipolla firstly introduced the encoder-decoder CNN architecture, with a network called SegNet [22]. The encoder produces hierarchical image representations with a CNN backbone such as VGG [23]. And, inversely, the decoder restores these low-dimensional features back to original resolution by a set of upsampling and convolution layers. The restored feature maps are finally used for pixel-label prediction [6]. The U-Net [24] developed by Ronneberger, Fischer, and Brox, initially proposed for biomedical image segmentation, is another popular example of an encoder-decoder CNN architecture. Particularly, U-Net uses skip

connections to combine deep semantic features from the decoder with the corresponding low-level fine-grained feature maps from the encoder, which results in a symmetric u-shaped architecture as can be seen in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4: Illustration of the U-Net architecture. Figure extracted from [24].

Semantic segmentation is a task that implies balancing local and global information. Meaning that, on the one hand, fine-grained or local information is critical to achieve good pixel-level accuracy. And, on the other hand, it is also necessary to integrate information from the global context of the image to allow the resolution of local ambiguities [10]. However, vanilla CNNs, due to the receptive fields of their units, only focus on local information. Many deep learning techniques have been proposed to make CNNs also aware of the global information: post-processing step with Conditional Random Fields (CRFs) [25], which allows the combination of both low-level image information with the output of multi-class inference systems that produce per-pixel class scores; dilated convolutions [26], also called atrous convolutions, which support exponentially expanding receptive fields without losing resolution; multi-scale aggregation [27], which keeps feature representation at multiple scales throughout the network and then merge them to produce a single output.

Another way to provide more spatial and contextual information is by the use and fusion of multimodal data. In the next section, I will examine the task of multimodal

semantic segmentation, reviewing the current fusion strategies as well as analysing the multimodal networks that best could adapt to the dataset at hand (see Section 3.1).

2.3 Multimodal semantic segmentation

Multimodality is a very natural concept for living creatures, which use both internal and external sensors (or senses in this case) to detect and discriminate among signals, communicate, disambiguate and add robustness to several life-death situations that need of rapid responses [28]. Furthermore, our brain also acts like a multimodal fusion system, synthesizing multiple sources of information for semantic perception and further decision making [11].

A multimodal setup is such one that has access to data from different modalities. And by modality I refer to each acquisition framework or detector obtaining information about the same scene [28]. These modalities are often used as complementary sensors in complex scenarios, such as the one at hand in this thesis (autonomous navigation in off-road scenarios), reducing the uncertainty in scene information and increasing robustness and accuracy in the model [11]. Figure 2.5 shows a diagram of the multimodal semantic segmentation pipeline.

Figure 2.5: A diagram representing the multimodal semantic segmentation pipeline. Figure extracted from [11].

In the recent years, a few factors have encouraged novel approaches into the field of multimodal fusion: the availability of multiple sensing modalities, the massive

amount of data and the increase in computing power [21] [11]. These fusion methods fully exploit hierarchical feature representations in an end-to-end manner [11] and in most cases, extend the unimodal algorithms with an effective fusion strategy, more on this in the subsection 2.3.2. Meaning that they derive from existing unimodal methods, usually taking neural networks such as VGGNet [29] or ResNet [23] as the backbone for data processing either as a whole or via separated parts [11].

In the following subsections, I will first analyse the advantages of having a multimodal setup, placing emphasis on multispectral sensors such as the one used to capture our dataset (see Section 3.1). Then a brief explanation of the different ways to approach fusion will be given. And finally an overview of the candidate models to tackle the task of working with and annotating the dataset captured is presented.

2.3.1 Sensing modalities

As mentioned in the previous section, the primary motivation for multimodal fusion is to learn the optimal joint representation from rich and complementary features of the same scene. For example, RGB cameras process efficiently information in good lighting conditions, while LiDAR sensors are more robust when it comes to arduous weather conditions such as fog, rain or snow. Compared to using a single modality, learning models that use multimodalities perform notably better [11].

Useful properties of NIR imaging

Figure 2.6: Benefits of using NIR imaging in challenging real-world scenes. Figure extracted from [30].

A modality of particular interest to our case is near-infrared (NIR), captured from multispectral sensors such as the one used in our setup (see Section 3.1). The intrinsic properties of NIR images make them relevant for semantic segmentation in general [31]. Infrared imaging shows higher contrast between natural and artificial objects than RGB images [30]. The intensity values in the NIR images are more consistent across a single material, and consequently across class regions, because of the distinctive reflectances of particular natural and man-made composites to NIR radiation [31]. Furthermore, less atmospheric scattering is captured in a NIR image [30]. These phenomena can be seen in the Figure 2.6 above. Moreover, in forested environments like the one in which our dataset was captured, the presence of chlorophyll, detected using NIR wavelength, in vegetation can be exploited allowing for better discernment of obstacles [2]. All these factors can potentially increase border accuracy at pixel-level predictions.

Due to the abundant presence of vegetation in off-road scenarios, and in the same way Valada et al. did for their *Freiburg Forest Dataset*, I compute global-based vegetation indices such as Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) or Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) to extract consistent spatial and global information [2]. This will be explained in more detail in Section 3.2.3. In our dataset, both near-infrared (NIR) and red edge bands were captured. Although most of the research regarding these bands have been conducted on the NIR band, the Red Edge band has also been proved to be key wavelength range in remote sensing that is also sensitive to vegetation conditions and can be used to support different vegetation parameter retrieval products [32]. With this thesis, among other things, I aim to evaluate the benefits of using such modalities and a multispectral sensor in addition to a standard RGB camera.

2.3.2 Fusion approaches

Deep neural networks represent features hierarchically and offer a wide range of choices to combine sensing modalities. Early works on the topic of multimodal semantic segmentation such as [2] only considered two types of fusion methodologies:

early fusion (or channel stacking) and late fusion. Actually, the initial attempt at fusing modalities for deep semantic segmentation, made by Couprie et al. [33] in 2013, was an example of an early fusion approach which concatenated RGB and depth data before feeding into a single network.

However, with the more recent research in the topic, later works such as the surveys [11] and [6] both released in 2021, consider further fusion techniques such as hybrid fusion or middle fusion. These two surveys present similar categorizations for the fusion approaches that primarily differ on the terminology of *hybrid* used by [11] or *middle* used by [6], although the last presents further more detailed schemes regarding middle/hybrid fusion. For that reason I favour the categorization made by [6], which is illustrated at Figure 2.7. Following I will review the characteristics of each of these fusion approaches:

Figure 2.7: An illustration of early fusion, late fusion, and several middle fusion methods. Figure extracted from [6].

Early fusion. This strategy combines directly the raw or pre-processed sensor data. As a result, the network can fully exploit the information of the raw data. The model can be trained end-to-end using an individual network so it has relatively low computation and memory requirements. However, that implies less model flexibility and the fact that the raw data is combined at the first step makes the network sensitive to spatial or temporal data misalignment caused by calibration errors or different sampling rates [6].

Late fusion. This approach by contrast takes and fuses the decision outputs of each modality-specific network. The model has more flexibility and modularity since when a new modality is added only its domain specific network requires to be trained, avoiding the need of retraining other networks. However, this comes at the cost of higher costs both in computation and memory. Moreover, it might toss rich intermediate features which may be of benefit when being fused [6].

Middle fusion. This scheme combines the strengths of early and late fusion fusing the feature representations from different sensing modalities at intermediate layers. This allows the network to learn cross modalities with different feature representations and at different depths. The fusion can occur at different steps and in different ways, such as combining only once at a middle layer, hierarchically throughout the training or in a "short-cut" fashion as can be seen in Figure 2.7 [6].

Feng et al. [6] did not find compelling evidence to say that one fusion method is superior from the others. Similarly, Zhang et al. [11] concludes that the optimal fusion strategy remains an open question. The performance of the models is greatly dependent on the modalities, data, and network architecture used. In the next subsection I will concentrate on the models that are better suited for off-road navigation. For more details on fusion approaches or the state-of-the-art models in each of those please view the very well compiled surveys [11] and [6] here reviewed.

2.3.3 Candidate models

One of the tasks at hand in this thesis is to train a multimodal semantic segmentation and to use it for annotating a new multispectral dataset captured. The choice for these two networks as candidates was made attending to the results obtained in [11], a very recent survey on multimodal semantic segmentation techniques. Here, Zhang et al. rated the models SSMA [21] and ACNet [34] as one of the best performing methods in the field and state-of-the-art in the task of RGB-D segmentation. Both these networks incorporate many advanced deep learning techniques such as multiscale feature aggregation, skip connections or attention mechanism, which are a

major reason for their exceptional performance [11]. Following a review of these two methods is presented as well as the reasoning behind the selection of one network over the other to carry out the work of this project.

Self-Supervised Model Adaptation (SSMA)

In their paper Self-Supervised Model Adaptation for Multimodal Semantic Segmentation [21], Valada, Mohan, and Burgard presented a fusion framework that dynamically adapts the fusion of modality-specific features maps. The proposed architecture consists of individual modality-specific encoder streams which are fused both at mid-level stages and at the end of the encoder streams using their proposed SSMA blocks [21] (see Figure 2.8. Another interesting contribution of their work was the efficient Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling (eASPP) module, a parameter-efficient alternative of the ASPP module [26], which has become very popular in most state-of-the-art architectures since it is able to capture long range context and multiscale information.

Figure 2.8: Topology of the encoder part of the multimodal fusion framework proposed at [21] with the use of SSMA blocks. Figure extracted from [21].

This model achieves state-of-the-art multimodal semantic segmentation performance on many datasets, including Freiburg Forest dataset which is the dataset used for support in order to annotate the new data (see Section 2.4). Originally, due

to this, this was the model chosen for the task but once I attempted the training I realized their source code was far from ideal. Firstly, the source code uses an old version of TensorFlow [35] which requires for a downgrade in my system or an update of the code. Secondly, due to its multi-stage procedure the training. Finally, their augmentation strategy is quite outdated and requires the generation of the augmentations in a previous step of the training, resulting in more time costs which are of big penalization in a project where so many tests and experiments need to be carried out with different modalities and data. Some of these drawbacks belong purely to the code itself and not to the architecture of the model, but unfortunately due to the time constrains and scope of this thesis a re-implementation from scratch of the model was not an option.

Attention Complementary Network (ACNet)

The Attention Complementary Network (ACNet) [34] proposed by Hu et al. is a novel fusion architecture based on attention mechanism [36]. Their fusion scheme is categorized as *early* by Zhang et al. [11], but I believe that is a misclassification since the network fuses RGB and depth features throughout the whole encoding phase resulting in a scheme closer to *short-cut middle* fusion as can be seen at Figure 2.10.

Figure 2.9: Architecture representation of ACNet [34]. Figure extracted from [34].

In ACNet, two independent branches based on ResNet [23] are dedicated to extract features for RGB and depth images. They utilize several of their proposed channel-attention modules, named Attention Complementary Module (ACM), to

extract weighted features from both RGB and depth branches which are determined by the amount of information they carry. And finally there is another branch to process the merged features [34]. Arguably, this architecture allows to gather features in an efficient manner without destroying original RGB and depth branches' inference.

ACNet achieved state-of-the-art results in both SUN-RGBD [37] and NYUDv2 [38] datasets, which are both multimodal RGB and depth datasets. Although originally the network was conceived to work uniquely with these two modalities, its capability can be extended to work with any other modalities such as NIR. Due to this high-performing results on RGB-D segmentation and aiming to explore the potential of this network with other modalities I finally chose to work with this network on annotating the new captured dataset. In addition, its architecture provides an easier training procedure compared to SSMA since all branches are trained simultaneously. In Section 3.5 I will explore how ACNet performs on the Freiburg Forest dataset [2] using different modalities and I will go through all modifications and improvements made to be able to adapt the network to both Freiburg Forest and the newly captured dataset.

2.4 Multimodal datasets

When it comes to developing methods for semantic segmentation or essentially any kind of deep learning task, one of the main elements to consider is the input data. A question one must ask is if there are any datasets available for the task. In this particular case the aim was to look for multimodal datasets with pixel-level semantic annotations in off-road navigation environments. In the recent years multimodal data are gaining traction among researchers in various domains and specially in the field of autonomous driving many datasets have been published, such as Cityscapes [39], Mapillary Vistas [40] or KITTI [41]. However, many of these datasets do not include multispectral data which will be the input data for our task or are not recorded in off-road unstructured terrains but in structured environments such as cities or main roads.

2.4.1 Multispectral datasets

Figure 2.10: Example image from the Freiburg Forest dataset showing the various spectra and modalities. Figure extracted from [2].

If we attend only to multispectral datasets which include NIR data the following should be highlighted. RANUS dataset [30], released to the public in 2018, consists of 40k pairs of RGB and NIR scenes captured across various urban, rural and campus roads and 4k manually annotated masks. In this dataset both buildings and natural landscapes are captured, resulting in ten different classes. Another important multispectral dataset is Freiburg Forest dataset [2], introduced by Valada et al., which was created with the purpose of addressing the task of semantic segmentation in unstructured forested environments. It contains 366 color, depth and NIR spatially aligned images along with some computed vegetation indexes due to the abundant presence of vegetation. The dataset incorporates segmentation ground-truth for six classes: *sky*, *trail*, *grass*, *vegetation*, *obstacle* and *void*. This later dataset, is very closely related to the one captured for this work (see Section 3.1), and consequently is the choice as the dataset to be used for the training.

Chapter 3

Methodology and experiments

3.1 Camera and recorded dataset specifications

The dataset at hand in this project, called Hungary Forest dataset, was recorded using the Parrot Sequoia multispectral sensor and RGB camera. The sensor was designed mainly for the use on drones to monitor agricultural crops. This is due to the capabilities of the sensor that is able to capture different wavelengths, Green, Red, Red-Edge and Near Infrared in order to highlight the vitality of plants [42]. Because of this same reason the sensor could be reasonably useful for its use on autonomous driving of vehicles on off-road forested scenarios where the surroundings of the road are gonna be to a great extent some kind of vegetation. Figure 3.1 shows a layout of the sensor. For further information see their official documentation [42].

Figure 3.1: Layout of the Parrot Sequoia sensor and RGB camera used to record the dataset. Image extracted from [42].

The multispectral sensor is composed by a global shutter with four bands (Green, Red, Red Edge and Near Infrared) that produces images with dimensions of 1280x960 pixels as well as a RGB camera that produces images of definition 4608x3456 pixels [42]. Figure 3.2 shows the raw recordings of a single frame. The recording of the dataset took place in Hungary during mid-November 2020. In total 2662 images were captured from each of the sensors in a span of approximately an hour while driving through forest roads.

Figure 3.2: Raw sensor recordings from the same frame. The sensor data from the multispectral camera (Green, NIR, Red, Red Edge) is recorded upside down. All images are scaled to the same dimension but the original dimensions are different between the multispectral sensor and the RGB camera.

3.2 Data preparation

Data preparation or preprocessing is a key component on every Machine Learning or Deep Learning problem and often has a significant impact on the generalization performance of supervised algorithm [43]. It is well known that data preparation is a time-consuming task within the learning pipeline and during this project that is no exception. For example, a few things that must be taken into consideration are that the images captured by the RGB sensor are of bigger dimension than the other sensors, or that the recording was started on a road instead of in the forest and some of the images are of out context, or that the sensors are not perfectly aligned, etc. The following subsections describe all the preparation steps taken to obtain the final dataset.

3.2.1 Data cleaning

The first step of the data processing pipeline is to do the data cleaning or data cleansing. Data cleaning refers to the process of identifying and removing corrupt or inaccurate records from the dataset in order to improve the quality of the dataset [44]. In this case the problems encountered were redundant or directly repeated images taken when the vehicle was stopped, images with noise or images that should not be part of the dataset (such as images taken during driving on perfectly paved road or highways).

For the removal of this redundant and non-corresponding images, our approach was to collect only the RGB images in a separate directory and then manually frame by frame attest if the image is dissimilar enough from the previous, understanding if the car was or not stopped at the moment of the recording of the frame. Once the definite collection of RGB images was defined, a simple Python script was programmed to erase the other bands from the original directory. Leaving the final dataset with 1252 images from 5 different modalities (Green, NIR, Red, Red Edge and RGB), which means that 53% of the images of the original data recording were removed. This could be done this way since the amount of images to clean was in the range of thousands. This would not be the case if the dataset at hand was a

collection of images in the range of hundreds of thousands or million of frames which is something frequent in these cases. For that a similarity criteria between images shall be defined and those images whose similarity with the previous frame does not surpass a certain threshold defined by the engineer or researcher should be erased.

3.2.2 Undistortion and image alignment

Another crucial preprocessing step when dealing with images taken from different sensors is image alignment, and that is specially important when the task is image segmentation since the spatial location of all objects in the sensors must match to provide pixel-accurate segmentation masks. But in order to properly align the different band images, one needs to handle first the lens distortion, which a non-linear generally radial projection of the surface points of objects onto the image plane [45]. For the correction of this, several different software packages exist. Here the software Pix4Dmapper [46] was used to generate the undistorted images.

Following to this, the undistorted images from the different bands are aligned with a homography-based warping method. To find the homographies between the sensors the OpenCV library [47] was used, specifically the function *create_SIFT* which utilizes the FLANN (Fast Library for Approximate Nearest Neighbors) [48] for feature matching and RANSAC (random sample consensus) [49] algorithm, to reject outliers, i.e. bad matches that reduce the precision of the alignment. This step was carried out on a few different image pairs (always taking a fixed band as reference) and then the average of the homographies were taken and applied via warping to the undistorted images.

Figure 3.3: Illustration of the steps followed to obtain aligned images: (a) image obtained directly from the RGB sensor, (b) result of the undistortion, (c) after applying the homography transform, (d) resulting final cropped image.

Figure 3.3 shows the process followed to align all images from the dataset, here only a single image from one sensor is presented for clarity purposes. The process is done with every image from all sensors. Due to the process of undistorting the images, some artifacts might appear close to the borders as can be seen in Figure 3.3(b). Also due to the warping carried out to align the images irregular black borders appear, showed at Figure 3.3(c). Finally those artifacts and black borders should be removed by zooming in and cropping the image as seen in Figure 3.3(d). After that, images are scaled down to the dimensions (768, 384) in order to alleviate computing costs for the training and to match the same dimensions used in the Freiburg Forest dataset [2].

3.2.3 Vegetation indices

So far we have obtained a cleansed and aligned dataset of images. We could initiate the training and experiments using just the data from the bands collected from the sensor but as shown in previous works, such as [2], computing some transformations on the bands such as vegetation indices can lead to better performance of the model. Vegetation indices (VIs) are spectral transformations of two or more bands conceived to boost the contribution of vegetation properties and allow reliable spatial and temporal inter-comparisons of terrestrial photosynthetic activity and canopy structural variations [50]. Since our images contain a lot of vegetation and following previous similar work [2] we compute a number of vegetation indices

shortly described below. Figure 3.4 shows RGB representation along with the result of the computation of some vegetation indices on the same frame.

Normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI)

The Normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) is the most frequently used VI and a popular forest health indicator [51]. NDVI reduces noise caused by changing sun angles, shadows and topography but has problems when faced variable atmospheric canopy background conditions [50]. The equation takes the form:

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{Red}}{\text{NIR} + \text{Red}}$$

Normalized difference water index (NDWI)

The Normalized difference water index (NDWI) utilizes the near-infrared radiation and visible green light to augment the presence of water features. As could be puddles on the road. Its formula is:

$$\text{NDWI} = \frac{\text{Green} - \text{NIR}}{\text{Green} + \text{NIR}}$$

Enhanced vegetation index (EVI)

The enhanced vegetation index (EVI) was proposed to optimize the vegetation signal with improved sensitivity in high biomass regions and better vegetation monitoring through a de-coupling of the canopy background signal and a reduction in atmospheric influences [50]. Its equation is given by:

$$\text{EVI} = 2.5 \times \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{Red}}{\text{NIR} + 6 \times \text{Red} - 7.5 \times \text{Blue} + 1}$$

Two-band Enhanced vegetation index (EVI2)

Many sensors as the one used for our recording lack the blue band needed to compute the three-band EVI version. In our case the EVI was computed by using the blue data RGB sensor but that is far from desirable since the quality of it will be affected. In addition, the blue band has a quite poor signal to noise ratio due to the nature

of the reflected energy in his part of the spectrum [52]. For that reason I mainly utilized the 2-band EVI or EVI2. Its defined by:

$$\text{EVI2} = 2.5 \times \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{Red}}{\text{NIR} + 2.5 \times \text{Red} + 1}$$

Figure 3.4: RGB and vegetation indices of the same frame

3.3 Data annotation

Data annotation is an essential step in any deep learning or machine learning task. The quality of data the annotations themselves determines the quality of the model. Data annotation, or data labelling, is a process that requires plenty of manual work and as such it proves to be a very tedious and time-expensive task. To alleviate this in the subsection 3.3.2 I present the strategy I followed to accelerate the process of manual annotation of images by using predictions from a model trained on a similar dataset and then by iteratively integrating the annotation images one is producing.

Our dataset is annotated using the same class labels used in the Freiburg Forest dataset [2]. Those classes are: *road* (gray), *grass* (light green), *vegetation* (dark green), *sky* (blue) and *obstacle* (black). The class names are quite self-explanatory. Figure 3.5 shows a sample RGB image from the Freiburg Forest dataset along with its pixel-level semantic label.

Figure 3.5: Sample RGB image from the Freiburg Forest dataset along with its corresponding label image where all classes are present.

Among the 1252 key frames selected during the data cleaning step, only some of them will be annotated due to both the cost in time of the task and redundancy of the images which are only separated by one second in time resulting in fairly similar images. The latter could even cause overfitting of the model during the training. The manual pixel-level annotations were carried by both my supervisor Gábor Kovács and myself using the tool described in the section 3.3.1. The annotation process was performed on every third frame (approximately) resulting in 414 images annotated. The results of the annotation can be seen in the Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6: Samples of the Hungary Forest dataset.

A common problem that might appear during the annotation process, even more frequent in tasks such as image segmentation, is the ambiguity in labels. Ambiguity in labels refers to the uncertainty upon which is the correct value for the label, in case of image segmentation which class should be assigned to the pixel x . The problem of this, is that if the labels are inconsistently defined, it is impossible to achieve a high test-set accuracy.

In our dataset, although the class names are self-explanatory, when it comes to the pixel level annotation then it is no longer unambiguous what is what. This ambiguity occurs mainly between the classes *vegetation* and *grass*, where it is not always simple to differentiate between them. The criteria that was followed was to decide on how tall was the grass, and to the understanding of the annotator, how traversible was the grass/vegetation in doubt: if it is considered to be short and easily traversible then the label would be *grass*; else, namely it is considered tall and difficult to traverse for the vehicle, the label should be *vegetation*. Similarly, it also existed some ambiguity between the classes of *road* and *grass* and between *sky* and

vegetation, here we respected what the model trained on the Freiburg Forest dataset [2] initially predicted as a general rule since the pixel-label separation between those classes were very accurate.

Figure 3.7: Class distribution in percentage in both datasets, Freiburg Forest and Hungary Forest.

The distribution of category classes showed at Figure 3.7 is interesting. The graphic exhibits how similar both datasets are. It is noteworthy to mention how the classes of *vegetation* and *sky* exchange dominance in the datasets both showing around 40% presence. This reflects the scenery in which the datasets were recorded. The class *vegetation* is the most common one in the Freiburg Forest dataset due to the presence of high and more condensed trees and high vegetation while in the case of Hungary Forest dataset, the class *sky* is the predominant since in the area recorded there is not that much abundance of high vegetation as well as possibly due to the setup of the camera that might point more upwards. Furthermore, the graphic also shows a small higher presence of the category *obstacle* in the Hungary Forest dataset, since it was recorded in the vicinity of an airport and some buildings or metal fences appear in a few of the samples.

In total 414 images were annotated, with a train-test split of 71-29% leaving

292 for the training dataset and 122 for the test dataset. Compared to the Freiburg Forest dataset [2] which contained 366 pixel-level annotations, where the train-test split was 63-37 resulting in 230 images for training purposes and 136 for evaluation. I opted for a more typical split in the deep learning community which assigns more substantially more samples to the training set achieving ratios of 70-30% or 80-20% [53]. The higher number of training samples would allow for better generalization of the predictions, while still having a sufficient amount of samples for the evaluation.

3.3.1 Tools for pixel-wise annotations

The task of image segmentation needs to be provided with pixel-wise annotation of images. For this annotation, there are several tools and products available, some of them are free of charge and some are not. Given the scope of this project paid options were withdrawn. Among the free ones, both labelme [54] and PixelAnnotationTool [55] arose as the best option. Labelme [54] is a polygonal annotation tool written in Python and uses Qt for the graphical interface. It allows for image annotation for polygon, rectangle, circle, line and point, even on videos. PixelAnnotationTool [55] is another great software that allows for image annotation. It is written in C++ and also uses Qt for the graphical interface.

The main strength of PixelAnnotationTool [55] relies on the method for annotating which uses the algorithm watershed marked of OpenCV [47]. The idea is to manually provide the marker with brushes and then to run the algorithm. After that, the user can correct the segmentation by drawing more markers where needed and run the algorithm again if desired. Making the process pseudo-manual and hence quicker. For that reason PixelAnnotationTool was the software chosen for this project. In Figure 3.8 an screenshot of the tool in action on the Hungary Forest dataset can be seen.

Figure 3.8: Screenshot of the PixelAnnotationTool [55] used to annotate the samples from the Hungary Forest dataset.

Furthermore, the tool allows for customization of its interface (options on the top left corner) by for example modifying the alpha mask or transparency factor of the mask so that more accurate annotation can be made. In addition, a Python script was developed to translate RGB annotations into one-channel label images which allowed to use predictions as an initial mask leading to a more agile process. This whole process is explained in the next section.

3.3.2 Speeding up the process

Manually annotating can be a tedious and very time-consuming task. It is also an expensive task since many hours of a human labour need to be spend on it, and it can be even more costly if the person behind the annotation is a highly skilled researcher or data scientist. Furthermore, the person can also feel that their current task is boring and unfulfilling. While starting to annotate this dataset that occurred and labelling times were often above 5 minutes mainly because of areas with a lot of detail such as tree branches or far away obstacles.

Figure 3.9: Flowchart representing the simple but effective strategy used to accelerate the annotation process.

The idea to accelerate this process is represented in the Figure 3.9 and consists of using the predictions of a model trained with a sufficiently similar dataset, in our case Freiburg Forest [2], to act as a first approximation of the actual ground truth to be constructed with the annotation tool. Then, iteratively include this new ground truths annotations into the training, either by continuing the training of the trained model with this smaller dataset or by integrating the new dataset on preparation with the old one and training from the beginning. That way the process will not be painting the mask from an empty canvas but rather fixing the parts of the sample that are inaccurately predicted. Slowly this process will produce more accurate predictions, closer to the ground truth, which will lead to less time spend correcting the inaccurate pixel labels.

This can reduce the labelling time by more than 80%, going from approximately 4-6 minutes when one needs to start the label from a empty canvas to 50-70 seconds per image when dealing with a prediction of a network trained with hundreds of samples of the same dataset. The estimates times were calculated by recording several dozens of labelling times both when the annotation process was started from nothing and when different stage predictions was used as first approximation of the ground truth.

Figure 3.10: Predictions at each step of the accelerated annotation process. First column (a) shows the predictions of a model trained only on the Freiburg Forest dataset; (b) adds 56 handpicked samples; (c) column shows the prediction with 174 samples from the same dataset; (d) adds the whole training data of 292 samples; the last column (e) shows the ground truth.

Figure 3.10 shows the predictions at different steps of the process for samples that were never included in the training set. Firstly, the predictions of a model trained only on the Freiburg Forest dataset were used, giving in most cases very inaccurate results far from the ground truth, that needed still quite a lot of time to be fixed until reaching a reasonable labelled image. The mean intersection over union (mIoU) at this point on the later constructed test set was 51.37% and the mean accuracy 78.46%. Secondly, above 50 samples were handpicked and annotated from the dataset covering several distinct scenarios within the recorded data. This samples were introduced along with the Freiburg Forest dataset in another training run and that translated masks much closer to the ground truth as can be appreciated in column (b). After that, the strategy was to annotate every tenth frame to be sure overfitting did not occur and following that since the dataset was not big and

robust enough every fifth frame was also annotated, visible at columns (c) and (d). The predictions now were much closer to the ground truth and much less time was needed to correct them. At this final point with the train dataset constructed the mIoU reached 88.17% and the mean accuracy 96.57%.

3.4 Data augmentation

In order to obtain robust deep neural network models a huge amount of data is required. However, as mentioned in the previous section acquiring and mostly annotating real-world data is not an easy task due to cost and time limitations. To overcome this it is usual to introduce data augmentation techniques which generate new samples by applying transformations on the already existing data with the objective of creating a larger dataset, preventing overfitting and increasing generalization capabilities [10].

Many transformations can be applied. Originally, in the ACNet implementation [34] random scaling, cropping and flipping were applied to both RGB and depth images. Furthermore, the color of RGB images was also randomly changed in HSV space. And finally both RGB and depth images are normalized separately. For my initial implementations I kept these and also added random rotation and skewing but, interestingly, when compared to the original augmentations, adding these further transformations did not translate to an improved performance, rather resulted in a detriment, lowering the accuracy and mIoU metric on the tests conducted. The reason for this event might be due to the resulting orientation of the road and similar objects that are not seen after in the evaluation meaning that it would only add noise to the training data. Also tested using less transformations but the original combination of augmentations always performed better. This shows that exploiting too much the regularization effect of this technique can actually lead to the model not learning enough which then translates into having worse prediction results. Consequently, one should not blindly add as many transformations as possible but rather try different combinations transformations to find the most appropriate for the task. All in all, for the following trainings I maintained the original trans-

formations used by [34], applying the geometric transformations to the RGB and to any secondary modality (EVI2, NIR, etc.) used.

3.5 Training the model

Once we have our dataset preprocessed, annotated and with a decided augmentation scheme we can consider the data to be prepared for the training. But having the data prepared is not enough to directly start the training of the model. The model needs to be adapted to the requirements of the dataset at hand, meaning that the hyperparameters for the model need to be fine-tuned.

Moreover, the ACNet model [34] implementation developed by Hu et al. as it is cannot be directly applied to the Freiburg Forest dataset [2] and our new captured dataset. Firstly, a new PyTorch *Dataset* class [56] needed to be implemented to read and store all the samples and their corresponding labels. Secondly, the model needed to be modality agnostic since the experiments needed to be conducted on different modalities, not only RGB plus depth as the model was originally conceived. For that further implementation was needed. Furthermore, I also added a code snippet that allows for evaluation on validation data during the training which better helps fine-tuning the data instead of only obtaining metrics on the training dataset and after the training is completed running metrics on the test dataset.

All instances of the ACNet training were carried out using the PyTorch library [56]. For all the experiments, ResNet50 [23] is used as the encoder, which is pre-trained on ImageNet [57] leveraging this way the technique of transfer learning. The trainings were performed using the NVIDIA 1080 Ti GPU with 11 GB of VRAM and took an average of 24 hours to finish. And for the training and evaluation I used the original train and test splits provided by the dataset.

3.5.1 Adapting the model to the dataset

As mentioned in Section 2.3.3 the network I decided to use for this work is ACNet [34]. Also as explained in Section 2.3.3, originally ACNet was conceived to be used

with the modalities of RGB and depth images, in the case of this project the model needs to be able to trained on different 1-channel modalities, such as EVI2 or NIR, in addition to the 3-channel RGB modality, making this way the network modality agnostic.

For this, a new Dataset class was created with the modalities parameterized, e.g. the modality can be changed by simply changing a string parameter that refers to the directory where the modality images are located. These directory names are maintained with respect to the original directory names used in the Freiburg Forest dataset. Furthermore, to better analyse the performance during training instead of only at the end, a validation code snippet was added in order to plot different metrics and intermediate predictions in TensorBoard [35]. The details and the implementation can be found here: <https://github.com/jesuscopado/ACNet>.

The implementation of the network, released by its authors, provides a training script for the datasets of SUN-RGBD [37] and NYUDv2 [38] which served as an initial approach for the hyper-parameters to be used here, but nonetheless one must find the optimal configuration of these parameters. As such, for example, the number of epochs proved to be too high for our dataset since the number of samples is much smaller than the previously mentioned datasets. So even though the training never showed clear signs of overfitting on training data when trained for 1500 epochs the training had already converged at 1000, slowing down the overall training time. Consequently, the number was reduced from 1500 down to 1000 epochs. It should be noted that due to hardware specifications of the GPU some parameters, such as the batch size such did not allow much space for calibration, and in general with training runs that last around a day it is complicated to reach the absolute optimal configuration. Following I present the changes in hyper-parameters which translated to the biggest noticeable improvements in performance.

Optimizer and schedulers

The predefined optimizer used by Hu et al. during the training of ACNet [34] for the training of both SUN-RGBD [37] and NYUDv2 [38] was SDG (Stochastic

Gradient Descent) [58] with momentum of 0.9 and weight decay of 10^{-4} . Experiments were done using also the Adam optimizer [59] but SDB proved to be better at all scenarios. As for the learning rate value and scheduling scheme, keeping the *LambdaLR* [56] but increasing slightly the number of epoch per learning rate decay keeping this way the learning rate with a higher value conduced to an increase in performance as can be seen in Figures 3.11 and 3.12. Even a bigger increase in performance was seen when I introduced into the training the cosine annealing with warm restarts scheduling [60], which by restarting the learning rate to its initial value is able to skip local minima. The figures 3.11 and 3.12 show only a few of the experiments done with the learning rate optimizers and schedulers.

Figure 3.11: Illustration of the learning rate values of the best performing schedulers. All other hyperparameters are fixed among these training runs. The y-axis shows the value of the learning rate and the x-axis shows the learning steps.

Figure 3.12: Graphic showing the mean intersection over union (mIoU) metric ran on the validation dataset during different runs of training varying the learning rate schedulers and fixing all other hyperparameters. The y-axis shows the value of mIoU rate and the x-axis shows the learning steps. Colors are maintained with respect to Figure 3.11.

Loss function

As for the loss function utilized, the ACNet paper [34] mentions the use of the Focal Loss [61] function but interestingly in their implementation the author seem to use the Cross Entropy Loss function. Due to this numerous experiments were run which proved that also in the case of the Freiburg Forest dataset Cross Entropy Loss achieved better results. The table below shows the evaluation metrics on some of these tests keeping all other hyperparameters fixed.

It is noteworthy to mention that due to the category distribution showed previously in Figure 3.7 a weight balancing on the loss function was needed. I used the inverse-frequency class weighting which is commonly used in similar segmentation problems [62]. In addition, I also tried utilizing different weights or manually increasing even more the weight of the class *obstacle* which always performed the worse on the Intersection over Union metric but these changes did not translate into any improvement, rather a decrease in performance since by focusing too much on this class the model would tend to excessively predict the aforementioned class category over the others.

Loss	γ	Road	Grass	Veg.	Sky	Obst.	mIoU	Acc.
Focal	0.5	88.49	88.47	90.58	92.55	40.72	80.16	94.78
Focal	1.5	88.21	88.74	90.88	92.52	43.41	80.75	94.88
CrossEntropy	-	88.76	88.81	90.85	92.74	43.63	80.96	94.94

Table 3.1: Evaluation results of the model using different losses for the trainings.

Keeping fixed all other hyperparameters and trained using RGB plus EVI2 modalities on the Freiburg Forest dataset. Columns 3 to 7 show the intersection over union (IoU) metric per class.

3.5.2 Evaluation results

Results on Freiburg Forest Dataset

Similarly as Valada, Mohan, and Burgard experimented on his SSMA experimentation on the Freiburg Forest dataset, the combination of modalities RGB plus EVI (or the equivalent EVI2) arose as the best performing one, see Table 3.2. Presumably, since as mentioned in Section 3.2.3 the vegetation index EVI allows for a better

Modalities	Road	Grass	Veg.	Sky	Obst.	mIoU	Acc.
RGB+Depth	88.40	89.09	91.32	92.68	37.02	79.70	95.07
RGB+EVI2	89.02	89.17	91.23	92.68	44.48	81.32	95.11
RGB+NDVI	88.15	88.83	90.89	92.47	42.83	80.64	95.10
RGB+NIR	89.16	89.33	91.12	92.52	41.90	80.81	94.91

Table 3.2: Evaluation results of the fine-tuned model using different modalities on the Freiburg Forest dataset. Columns 2 to 6 show the intersection over union (IoU) metric per class.

Figure 3.13 shows metrics of the best performing configuration of modalities and hyperparameters of the ACNet training on the Freiburg Forest dataset. It also shows the typical behaviour during the training in which both training loss, validation loss and accuracy quickly converge within the very first epochs but the mean intersection over union metric (run on the validation dataset) takes more time to converge mainly

due to the less frequent *obstacle* class as presented in Figure 3.7. The validation loss even starts to increase possibly showing signs of overfitting the training data but the continuous adjustments on the IoU of all classes make the mIoU keep on increasing. This is probably due to the class-balancing weight applied to the loss function which turn the emphasis in correctly predicting the less common classes.

Figure 3.13: Training and evaluation metrics of the ACNet model on Freiburg Forest dataset (RGB plus EVI2).

Results are very close to the state-of-the-art results of 83.9% mIoU achieved

by the SSMA model [21] on modalities RGB and EVI while being ACNet a much lighter model and having much less parameters, having just 11.66 million parameters instead of 55.44 million parameters as the SSMA model [21]. As such it is a more suitable option for online inference during autonomous navigation vehicles which cannot carry a powerful GPU.

Results on Hungary Forest Dataset

Modalities	Road	Grass	Veg.	Sky	Obst.	mIoU	Acc.
RGB+EVI2	92.07	90.20	90.67	98.27	69.61	88.17	96.57
RGB+NDVI	89.61	89.27	90.89	97.83	55.26	84.30	96.06
RGB+NDWI	90.55	89.31	89.65	97.94	64.35	86.36	96.23
RGB+NIR	87.56	88.35	91.12	97.76	65.62	85.54	95.73
RGB+REG	89.87	89.47	89.80	97.44	65.61	86.36	95.70

Table 3.3: Evaluation results of the fine-tuned model using different modalities on the Hungary Forest dataset. Columns 2 to 6 show the intersection over union (IoU) metric per class.

Once more the combination of the modalities RGB and EVI2 proved to be the best performing one. Interestingly, the secondary modalities that came after EVI2 were NDWI and Red Edge (REG) obtaining both 86.36. The modality of RGB plus NDVI scored lower metrics that might be due to the stochastic nature of the optimizer. With a bigger time frame several runs should be conducted with the same training configuration to either collect the best result or the average of them.

These higher numbers in terms of both accuracy and mIoU on this dataset compared to the Freiburg Forest dataset might indicate overfitting since the dataset was recorded on a single day which might lead to less variability in weather or lightning conditions that would affect shadows and sun angles. Rather than on different days as was done with the Freiburg Forest dataset, where the collected data belonged to the three different days allowing for presumably more variability. In the next and

final section of the chapter the results of experiments being done combining both datasets are presented.

Combining both datasets

Dataset	Road	Grass	Veg.	Sky	Obst.	mIoU	Acc.
Freiburg	88.19	90.88	90.89	92.66	43.93	80.81	94.87
Hungary	96.14	94.33	94.56	99.74	75.07	91.97	98.21

Table 3.4: Evaluation results on Freiburg Forest and Hungary Forest datasets of the ACNet model with modalities RGB and EVI2 trained using both datasets.

Columns 2 to 6 show the intersection over union (IoU) metric per class.

The table 3.4 shows the results of training the model with the modalities RGB plus EVI2 (the highest performing configuration) using a dataset composed by the combination of the training sets from both Freiburg Forest and Hungary Forest datasets. The results on the Hungary Forest dataset are even higher than when training with only its training data seemingly showing the bias of the annotators when manually labelling the samples. Since as explained in section 3.3.2 the predictions that serve as a draft or first approximation of the ground truth labels that would form the Hungary Forest dataset came from a model that was trained using the combination of both datasets. This bias would affect mainly the ambiguities mentioned in section 3.3. The results from the Freiburg Forest dataset are similar to the ones presented in the table 3.13 which implies that the samples from the Hungary Forest dataset do not deteriorate the quality of the predictions probably due to the reason that both datasets are quite alike.

Interestingly, the evaluation results when trained uniquely on the opposite datasets showed at the table 3.5 might point at the Hungary Forest dataset being more robust since it achieves better quality predictions on unseen scenarios. But this results can also be affected by the bias mentioned in the previous paragraph. In order to correctly examine their robustness a third similar off-road dataset should be introduced for the evaluation and comparison.

Train.	Eval.	Road	Grass	Veg.	Sky	Obst.	mIoU	Acc.
Freiburg	Hungary	46.84	46.65	64.87	85.93	12.55	51.37	78.46
Hungary	Freiburg	70.78	77.44	84.66	86.48	11.76	66.21	89.62

Table 3.5: Evaluation results on Freiburg Forest and Hungary Forest datasets of the ACNet model with modalities RGB and EVI2 trained using the opposite datasets. Columns 3 to 7 show the intersection over union (IoU) metric per class.

A reason for this low metrics is presumably the difference in the color tone of the grass, being brown or yellowish in the case of Hungary Forest dataset instead of intense green in the case of Freiburg Forest dataset. The combination of both datasets will probably translate into robust and more accurate predictions in other places and along all seasons.

Chapter 4

Conclusions

The results of ACNet [34] trained on Freiburg Forest dataset were very close to state-of-the-art results obtained by Valada, Mohan, and Burgard with their SSMA model [21] despite the fact that ACNet has far less parameters as discussed in Section 3.5.2. The modalities that worked best in combination were RGB along with EVI2 as in the case of the SSMA model [21] due to the enhanced detection of vegetation in the samples provided by using this vegetation index. This work done in this thesis allowed to demonstrate that the multimodal model ACNet [34], initially engineered to work on RGB plus depth images, could also be extended for its use with any other single channel modality such as EVI, NDVI or near-infrared.

Data labeling can be a very time-consuming task, but by using tactics as the one presented here in this project (see section 3.3.2), the process proves to be a bit less tedious. The labeling of a single image went down from five minutes when no model prediction used as approximation of the label image was given to less than a minute in most cases when an estimation of the final annotation was given since the annotator in this later case only needs to polish the inaccurate pixels. As a result of this annotation process a new dataset, called Hungary Forest dataset, has been created. The author hopes for it to be of contribution to future research done for off-road autonomous operations. Still, the fact of having to spend so much time and effort in the annotation process only slows down research done, specially noticeable

in the field of semantic segmentation where the annotation need to be pixel-accurate. Strategies like the one proposed at 3.3.2 are needed but bigger free and open source frameworks would be even better.

4.1 Future work

One of the most important pillars for training Deep Learning models, if not the most important one, is the data itself. But not only the quantity of data is relevant, also its quality, and for that we not only need high resolution images for example, we require enough variety in our data for our model to be more consistent and robust allowing it to generalize and predict better on different input scenarios. For this reason, I suggest as future work to gather more data, e.g. multispectral images, under different and more adverse conditions, such as foggy or stormy days. Since the autonomous vehicle needs to be prepared for this conditions or for sudden changes in the weather too.

Similarly, it will be useful to have data recorded across all seasons of the year. As explained in section 3.5.2, one of the reasons I believe the network trained solely on Freiburg Forest dataset failed to correctly predict on most of the images of the Hungary Forest dataset was due to the difference in color tone of the grass, being brown or yellowish in the case of Hungary Forest dataset (recorded in Autumn) instead of intense green in the case of Freiburg Forest dataset.

As showed in section 3.5.2 one of the classes was falling behind in the mean over union metric, and that was the obstacle class. As mentioned before, this was a result of very infrequent cases in the dataset where this class was present. To correct and improve this metric more images that contain obstacles should be added to the dataset for the model to rightly predict on different obstacles that may appear in the road, such as animals or construction sites.

Furthermore, using methods based on semi-supervised learning techniques and deep adversarial networks such as [63] that utilize unannotated images for training effective segmentation models would be a great way to make use of the data without

labeling that is much easier to acquire. These methods as well as utilizing multimodal pipelines as the one used in this work promise great advancements in the field of semantic scene understanding in off-road scenarios.

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